

Intergovernmental Fiscal Transfers and Regional Economic Performance: Evidence from Papua Province, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Economic inequality between regions in Indonesia, particularly between Papua and other regions, remains a strategic issue despite Papua's abundant natural resources. Transfers of funds from the central government, such as the General Allocation Fund (GAF), Revenue Sharing Fund (RSF), and Special Autonomy Fund (SAF), are expected to boost regional economic growth. This study aims to analyze the influence of GAF, RSF, and SAF on Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) of districts/cities in Papua Province. Secondary data were obtained from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) and the Ministry of Finance for the period 2013–2022. The analysis method used panel data regression with a Fixed Effect Model selected through the Chow and Hausman test. The results show that GAF and RSF have a significant positive effect on GRDP, while SAF has no significant effect. This finding indicates that general transfers and revenue sharing can improve regional economic performance, while special autonomy funds have not yet provided the expected impact, likely due to constraints in governance and utilization effectiveness. Regional governments need to optimize the use of GAF and RSF for productive public spending and improve the SAF management mechanism to make a real contribution to Papua's economic growth.

KEYWORDS: Gross Regional Domestic Product, General Allocation Fund, Revenue Sharing Fund, Special Autonomy Fund, Papua.

INTRODUCTION

Regional economic development is a key pillar in achieving sustainable national economic growth. Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) measures a region's economic performance, reflecting the total added value generated by all business units in a region (Prasetyo et al., 2020; BPS, 2023). According to Adisasmitha (2013), GRDP is not only a measure of regional economic success but also a reflection of a region's contribution to national development.

However, in Indonesia, the focus of economic policy remains centered on achieving Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at the national level. Meanwhile, GRDP targets at the regional level have not yet become a primary focus in development planning. Data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS, 2023) shows that the contribution of GRDP to national GDP in the fourth quarter of 2023 was still concentrated in Java at 57.05%, followed by Sumatra at

22.01%, Kalimantan at 8.49%, Sulawesi at 7.10%, Bali and Nusa Tenggara at 2.77%, and finally Maluku and Papua at 2.58%. This concentration indicates a suboptimal distribution of economic development across regions.

Based on Figure 1, Eastern Indonesia has the lowest average GRDP per capita compared to the Western and Central Regions. This condition indicates a relatively underdeveloped economy in the eastern region, particularly Papua. Arham (2019) attributes this underdevelopment to limited infrastructure, resulting in high economic costs. Papua, as the largest province in the eastern region, has even recorded a GRDP far below the national average in recent years (BPS, 2022). This is despite the fact that theoretically, this region has long-term investment potential in leading sectors such as mining, energy, construction, and transportation and warehousing (Budiono, 2016; Wai & Widayat, 2017).

Figure 1. Average GRDP per capita based on constant 2010 prices
 Source: Central Statistics Agency (2023)

Based on Table 1, Papua Province had a GRDP gap of more than 150 trillion Rupiah compared to the national average between 2018 and 2022. This gap raises the urgency of fiscal policies capable of optimizing Papua's natural resource potential, including the mining, forestry, and maritime sectors (BPS, 2023; OECD, 2022).

Economic disparities between regions are one of the reasons for the emergence of regional autonomy policies in Indonesia, which are regulated by Law Number 22 of 1999

and Law Number 25 of 1999, later amended by Law Number 23 of 2014 and Law Number 1 of 2022 concerning Financial Relations between the Central and Regional Governments. Within the framework of fiscal decentralization, regional governments obtain funding sources through Regional Original Revenue (ROR), Transfer Funds from the Central Government, and other legitimate ROR (Arham, 2019; Huda, 2014).

Table 1. Average Difference between National GDP and Papua's GRDP (in Trillions of Rupiah)

Year	Average National GDP	Papua's GRDP	Difference
2018	309.93	159.71	150.22
2019	325.36	134.57	190.79
2020	318.75	137.79	180.96
2021	330.57	158.67	171.89
2022	348.23	172.90	175.32

Source: Central Statistics Agency (2023)

Transfer funds are a crucial instrument for driving regional economic growth, especially in regions still dependent on central funding. Law Number 1 of 2022 establishes six types of transfer funds: Revenue Sharing Funds (RSF), Special Allocation Funds (SAF), General Allocation Funds (GAF), Special Funds (SF), Special Autonomy Funds (SAF), and Village Funds (VF). Various studies have shown mixed results regarding the effectiveness of transferring funds to GRDP. For example, Ningsih and Noviaty (2019) found a negative effect of the Balancing Fund on GRDP at the provincial level. Meanwhile, Hutapea and Priharjanto (2022) found that the General Allocation Fund (GAF) and Regional Revenue Sharing (RRS) positively influenced regional economic growth. Research by Anwar et al. (2018) specifically for Papua found that the Special Autonomy Fund (SAF) positively influenced GRDP. However, the disparity in these research results indicates that

other factors, such as governance effectiveness, human resource quality, and infrastructure, moderate this relationship (Fahrudin, 2022; Utami et al., 2023).

Therefore, a study is needed that simultaneously examines the effects of the General Allocation Fund (GAF), Regional Revenue Sharing (RRS), and Special Autonomy Funds (SAF) on GRDP of regency/city in Papua over a long period, linking them to the fiscal federalism theory (Musgrave, 1959; Oates, 1972), which emphasizes the efficient allocation of public resources through decentralization. This research aims to fill this gap and provide relevant policy recommendations for improving the economic performance of special autonomous regions.

The General Allocation Fund (GAF) aims to provide funds based on objectively calculated fiscal needs and fiscal capacity. According to fiscal decentralization theory, Regional Transfer Funds (RSF) can increase regional fiscal

capacity to finance development and improve public services. Research by Sirait and Handra (2020) shows that the General Allocation Fund (GAF) has a significant positive effect on increasing GRDP in various regions in Indonesia, including Papua. The GAF is predicted to have a significant positive effect on GRDP. Several research findings indicate that increases in the GAF are correlated with increases in GRDP in various regions. In a study conducted by Oktafia et al. (2018) in East Java Province, the GAF found a significant positive effect on regency/city GRDP. Based on this, the first research hypothesis in this study is as follows:

H1: The General Allocation Fund (GAF) has a positive effect on GRDP.

Revenue Sharing Funds (RSF) are allocated based on regional revenue from natural resources and taxes. RSF can increase GRDP if managed properly and reinvested in the local economy. Previous research, such as that conducted by Hutapea and Priharjanto (2022), indicates that RSF has a positive effect on regional economic growth. The Regional Revenue Sharing Fund (RSF) is expected to have a significant positive impact on GRDP. RSF can increase regional fiscal capacity, which in turn increases GRDP. Research conducted by Ningsih and Noviaty (2019) in South Sumatra Province showed that although RSF had no significant effect on GRDP partially, when combined with other variables, it can increase GRDP. Furthermore, research by Hutapea and Priharjanto (2022) also showed that RSF has a positive impact on GRDP. Based on this argument, the second hypothesis of this study is as follows:

H2: RSF has a positive impact on GRDP

Special Autonomy Funds (SAF) are provided to regions with special autonomy status, such as Papua, with the aim of supporting the implementation of special autonomy and accelerating development. Anwar et al. (2018) found that the SAF had a significant positive impact on GRDP in Papua, although challenges in managing funds and infrastructure remain major obstacles. The SAF is expected to have a significant positive impact on GRDP. Regions with allocated SAF tend to experience better economic growth. Anwar et al. (2018) found that the SAF had a significant positive impact on GRDP in Papua. This study shows that increasing the SAF contributes positively to regional economic growth. Based on this, the third research hypothesis is as follows:

H3: SAF has a positive effect on GRDP

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative correlational approach aimed at revealing correlative relationships between variables, referring to the tendency for variations in one variable to be followed by variations in another (Kusumastuti, 2020). The variables that are correlated are the dependent and independent variables. The dependent variable in this study is Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP). Considering that the research aims to measure economic growth, the data used is GRDP at Constant Prices published by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS). The independent variables in this study are the realization of transfers from General Allocation Funds (GAF), Revenue Sharing Funds (RSF), and Special Autonomy Funds (SAF).

Table 2. Operational Definitions of Variables

Variables	Variable Definition	Size	Scale
Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP)	The total value of final goods and services produced by all economic units in a region.	Calculation based on non-mining expenditures per regency/city within Papua Province	Ratio
General Allocation Funds (GAF)	Regional transfer funds are allocated to reduce disparities in financial capacity and public services between regions.	Calculated based on the fiscal gap per regency/city within Papua Province	Ratio
Revenue Sharing Funds (RSF)	Regional transfer funds are allocated based on a percentage of specific revenues in the State Budget.	Consists of total realized transfers of Tax Revenue Sharing Funds (RSF) and Natural Resources Revenue Sharing Funds (RSF) per regency/city within Papua Province	Ratio
Special Autonomy Funds (SAF)	Regional transfer funds are allocated to specific regions to fund the implementation of special autonomy as stipulated in the Law on Special Autonomy.	Realized Transfers of Special Autonomy Funds per regency/city within Papua Province	Ratio

Source: Mankiw (2018) and Law Number 1 of 2022 (Processed)

The population used is 29 regencies and cities in Papua Province. The sampling technique used is purposive sampling, with selection based on specific criteria related to population characteristics (Adisasmita, 2013). The criteria in question are the availability of research data. Data is available from 29 regencies/city in Papua province from 2013 to 2022. Data sources were obtained from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) website (<https://www.bps.go.id/>) and the Ministry of Finance website, specifically through the website of the Ministry of Finance's Directorate General of Fiscal Balance (<http://www.djpk.kemenkeu.go.id/>).

The data analysis method used was panel data regression. The use of panel data regression is adapted to the

type of data that simultaneously has cross-sectional (regency/city) and time series (year) characteristics. There are at least three possible panel data regression models to choose from: the Common Effect Model (CEM), the Fixed Effect Model (FEM), and the Random Effect Model (REM) (Rifkhan, 2023). Of these three models, only one will be selected to test the research hypotheses. The model selection method used was the Chow Test, the Hausman Test, and the Lagrange Multiplier Test (Rifkhan, 2023). Meanwhile, testing the feasibility of the model uses the F-test, t-test, and measures how large the coefficient of determination of the model is.

Table 3. Regencies and Cities in Papua Province

No	Name of Regency/City	No	Name of Regency/City
1	Merauke Regency	16	Sarmi Regency
2	Jayawijaya Regency	17	Keerom Regency
3	Jayapura Regency	18	Waropen Regency
4	Nabire Regency	19	Supiori Regency
5	Kepulauan Yapen Regency	20	Mamberamo Raya Regency
6	Biak Numfor Regency	21	Nduga Regency
7	Paniai Regency	22	Lanny Jaya Regency
8	Puncak Jaya Regency	23	Mamberamo Tengah Regency
9	Mimika Regency	24	Yalimo Regency
10	Boven Digoel Regency	25	Puncak Regency
11	Mappi Regency	26	Dogiyai Regency
12	Asmat Regency	27	Intan Jaya Regency
13	Yahukimo Regency	28	Deiyai Regency
14	Pegunungan Bintang Regency	29	Jayapura City
15	Tolikara Regency		

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Papua Province has a diverse and challenging geography, covering an area of approximately 768,000 km², of which 71% is tropical rainforest with numerous valleys and high mountains. These geographical challenges complicate infrastructure development, such as the construction of the Trans-Papua Highway, which requires clearing forests and filling swamps. The uneven population distribution, consistent with the geographical conditions, adds complexity to the provision of public services and economic development. Socially, Papuan society consists of strong indigenous communities scattered across small groups. Marginalization and discrimination against indigenous people, as well as human rights violations, remain major issues. The disparity in access to public services between urban and rural areas is also a serious concern (Fauzi et al., 2019).

Economically, despite Papua's abundant natural resources, the province faces significant challenges in economic development and public welfare. The poverty rate in Papua is the highest in Indonesia, with significant disparities between regions. Research by Oktavia et al. (2021) showed that there was beta and sigma convergence between districts/cities in Papua during the 2010-2020 period, meaning that poorer or more disadvantaged regions tended to experience faster economic growth than more developed regions, thus narrowing the economic gap between regions over time. However, problems such as a lack of coordination between the central and regional governments and the low quality of human resources remain major obstacles. Infrastructure development, which was expected to increase economic potential, has not had a significant impact on job creation or driving economic growth. Therefore, natural resource management and the development of sectors such as agriculture, fisheries, and tourism need to be improved to

improve economic conditions in Papua Province (Fauzi et al., 2019).

The three research variables: General Allocation Fund (GAF), Revenue Sharing Fund (RSF), and Special Autonomy Fund (SAF) play a crucial role in economic development in Papua. All three are capable of enhancing

regional fiscal capacity, supporting economic growth, reducing poverty, and improving the region's Human Development Index (HDI) (Alvaro & Zahara, 2019). The statistical descriptions of the three variables are presented in Table 4, including the GRDP variable.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of Research Variables (in Millions of Rupiah)

Statistik Deskriptif	PDRB	GAF	RSF	SAF
Mean	2.966.456,0	646.503,7	102.775,7	92.473,5
Median	1.364.052,0	632.682,8	47.878,9	100.100,0
Maximum	23.611.086,0	1257.424,0	4.163.917,0	214.243,7
Minimum	498.813,2	336.371,0	21.170,7	29.020,0
Std. Dev.	4.122.611,0	152.703,6	319.391,1	32.898,2
n	290	290	290	290

Source: Data processed (2025)

The regency/city with the highest GRDP was Jayapura City in 2022, with a value of 23,611.086 billion rupiah, while the lowest GRDP was Yalimo Regency in 2013, with a value of 498.813 billion rupiah. The range of GRDP values is 23,112.272 billion rupiah, and the standard deviation is 4,122.611 billion rupiah. These two very large values indicate significant disparities in economic activity between regency/city in Papua province.

Based on Figure 2, the average GRDP of regency/city in Papua Province fluctuated from 2013 to 2022. From 2013 to 2019, the average GRDP showed a consistent upward trend. However, in 2020, the average GRDP declined, coinciding with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. The impact of the pandemic on the economy continued into 2021, but the average GRDP finally increased again in 2022, indicating a post-pandemic economic recovery.

Figure 2. Graph of Average GRDP of REgency/City in Papua Province

Source: Data processed (2025)

Figure 3 shows fluctuations in the amount of funds received each year. The average GAF shows a consistent increasing trend from Rp540,177,740,000.00 in 2013 to Rp705,994,370,000.00 in 2019, then decreased in 2020 to Rp636,799,260,000.00, and stabilized until 2022 at around Rp627,142,240,000.00. The average RSF experienced greater variation, starting from Rp60,698,620,000.00 in 2013,

increasing sharply in 2021 to Rp131,578,980,000.00, and reaching a peak in 2022 at Rp262,536,860,000.00. The average SAF also fluctuates, with a peak value of Rp79,455,860,000.00 in 2013, then peaking at Rp151,549,640,000.00 in 2022 after several years of stability at around Rp106,523,440,000.00.

Figure 3. Graph of Average GAF, RSF, and DAK of Regency/City in Papua Province
 Source: Data processed (2025)

The panel data regression model selection using the Chow and Hausman tests is shown in Table 5. Based on the test results, the probability value for the cross-section F-statistic is 0.0000, and for the cross-section Chi-square is 0.0000, both of which are less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected, indicating that the Fixed Effects Model is more appropriate for this data. The next step is to conduct a Hausman test to determine whether the fixed effects model or the Random Effects Model is more appropriate. Based on the test results, the probability value for the cross-section Chi-square statistic is 0.0175, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected,

indicating that the Fixed Effect Model is more appropriate for this data.

Classical assumption tests on the selected model (Fixed Effect Model) are necessary to ensure that the model meets the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model assumptions. According to Gujarati and Porter (2009), the basic assumptions that must be met are normality, homoscedasticity, and the absence of multicollinearity. The autocorrelation assumption does not need to be met. As stated by Basuki and Prawoto (2022), autocorrelation assumption tests are only performed for time series data, as panel data does not qualify as time series data.

Table 5. Selection of Panel Data Regression Models

Jenis Uji	Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Uji Chow	Cross-section F	305.263921	(28,258)	0.0000
	Cross-section Chi-square	1023.746314	28	0.0000
Uji Hausman	Cross-section random	10.129400	3	0.0175

Source: Data processed (2025)

Table 6. Correlation Coefficient between Independent Variables

Variabel	GAF	RSF	SAF
GAF	1		
RSF	-0.05200	1	
SAF	0.09027	0.02351	1

Source: Data processed (2025)

The normality assumption test uses the Jarque-Bera Test, which combines the skewness and kurtosis tests of the residual distribution (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). The Jarque-Bera value from the normality test is 3.410609 with a

probability of 0.181717, greater than the alpha value of 0.05, so the residuals of the model are normally distributed and the normality assumption is met. Meanwhile, the multicollinearity assumption is also met. This is indicated by

the relatively small correlation coefficients between the independent variables GAF, RSF, and SAF (none above 0.8). The results of the heteroscedasticity test using the Glejser method indicate the presence of heteroscedasticity. However, this problem can be solved using the Seemingly Unrelated Regression (SUR) method, which means the

homoscedasticity assumption has been met (Greene, 2012). The SUR method allows data transformation to be homoscedastic through a two-stage Generalized Least Squares (GLS) approach, resulting in more accurate estimates.

Table 7. Fixed Effect Model Regression Output

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1893087	413412,0	4,579177	0,0000
GAF	1,630849	0,626772	2,601979	0,0098
RSF	1,151130	0,286269	4,021145	0,0001
SAF	-1,073693	1.040485	-1,031916	0,3031
R-squared =	0,977271			
Adjusted R-squared =	0,974540			
F-statistic =	357,8366			
Prob(F-statistic) =	0,000000			

Source: Data processed (2025)

The model fit test (F-test) helps determine whether the constructed regression model can fully explain the variation in the dependent variable (GRDP). Based on Table 7, the F-test indicates that all independent variables (GAF, RSF, and SAF) simultaneously have a significant effect on the dependent variable (GRDP). Meanwhile, based on Table 4.4, the R2 value is 0.977271, and the Adjusted R2 value is 0.974540. This means that 97.75% of the variation in the dependent variable (GRDP) can be explained by the independent variables (GAF, RSF, and SAF) in the model.

The General Allocation Fund (GAF) variable has a probability value of 0.0098, which is less than the α level of significance (0.05). This indicates that the GAF has a significant effect on GRDP. The Revenue Sharing Fund (RSF) variable also shows a significant effect on GRDP with a probability value of 0.0001, which is less than α (0.05). This significant influence indicates that RSF plays an important role in determining variations in GRDP, in line with the results of the GAF variable. However, the Special Autonomy Fund (SAF) variable has a Prob. value of 0.3031, which is greater than α (0.05). This means that SAF does not have a significant effect on GRDP. Thus, it can be concluded that only the GAF and RSF variables individually have a significant effect on GRDP, while SAF does not have a significant effect.

Discussion

The General Allocation Fund (GAF) variable has a regression coefficient of 1.630849 with a probability value of 0.0098. This indicates that the General Allocation Fund (GAF) has a significant positive effect on GRDP. Thus, an increase in the GAF significantly contributes to an increase in

GRDP. These results support the first hypothesis (H1), which states that the General Allocation Fund (GAF) has a significant positive effect on GRDP. This finding aligns with other studies that have also evaluated the effect of the GAF on GRDP in various regions, such as the study by Oktafia et al. (2018) in East Java Province, which found that the GAF had a significant positive effect on GRDP.

This study demonstrates that the allocation of funds from the central government, particularly the GAF, is effective in increasing regional economic activity and contributing to an increase in GRDP. This similarity suggests that the General Allocation Fund policy has similar effects across provinces, despite differences in economic conditions and regional characteristics. Furthermore, research by Sasea et al. (2020) in West Papua Province also found that the General Allocation Fund (GAF) had a significant positive effect on GRDP. However, they highlighted that GAF contributions were primarily directed toward infrastructure development, such as roads and bridges, that support regional economic growth. This research emphasizes the importance of regional context and local characteristics in evaluating the effectiveness of fiscal policy and allocating funds. However, research by Fahrudin (2022) in Papua Province showed that the General Allocation Fund (GAF) had a significant negative effect of -0.1487504 on economic growth. He explained that this negative effect was driven by the use of GAF for decentralization financing, which was allocated more for indirect spending, such as personnel expenditures, rather than direct spending that directly impacts community economic growth.

The positive effect of the General Allocation Fund (GAF) on Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) in

regency/city in Papua Province can be explained by several key factors, including increased regional fiscal capacity, which allows for greater investment in public infrastructure, and socio-economic spending that improves community welfare. Good infrastructure, such as roads, bridges, and other public facilities, is a crucial foundation for stimulating economic activity, connecting remote areas, and attracting new investment. This is supported by research showing that infrastructure improvements directly impact regional economic growth by creating a conducive environment for business and trade (Nisa, 2017).

The effective and efficient use of the General Allocation Fund (GAF) by local governments also directly contributes to economic productivity. In the Papuan context, GAF allocations are often used to fund social and economic spending that directly impacts the quality of life of the community. Programs such as education, health, and local economic empowerment are more easily implemented with GAF support. Research by Sasea et al. (2020) in West Papua Province also supports this view, where the GAF was used for infrastructure development that supported regional economic growth. Therefore, GAF allocation that is well-targeted and aligned with regional needs can accelerate economic development and increase GRDP. The effectiveness of GAF use in supporting local economic growth is also supported by the theory of fiscal decentralization, which states that resource allocation closer to local needs tends to be more effective and efficient.

The Revenue Sharing Fund (RSF) variable has a coefficient of 1.151130 with a probability value of 0.0001. This indicates that RSF has a significant positive effect on Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP). Thus, an increase in RSF significantly contributes to an increase in GRDP. These results support the second hypothesis (H2), which states that the Revenue Sharing Fund (RSF) has a significant positive effect on GRDP.

These results align with research by Hutapea and Priharjanto (2022), which found that RSF had a significant positive effect on economic growth in 34 provinces in Indonesia, while the Special Allocation Fund (DAK) showed a negative effect. This indicates that, in general, RSF can increase GRDP in various regions in Indonesia, although there are differences in the effects of other components of the Balancing Fund. However, these results differ from the findings of research by Ningsih and Noviaty (2019), which examined the effect of Regional Original Revenue (PAD) and the Balancing Fund on economic growth in South Sumatra Province. The study shows that the Regional Revenue Sharing Fund (RSF), as part of the Balancing Fund, has an insignificant impact on economic growth in the region. This indicates that the effectiveness of RSF may vary depending on the regional context and local economic characteristics.

Furthermore, this study's findings differ from those of Fahrudin (2022), who found that RSF had no impact on

economic growth in Papua. This is explained by the specific RSF types that have earmarks for their management, such as the RSF for health, and the block grant nature of tax and non-tax RSF. Suboptimal fund utilization, the large amount of indirect spending compared to direct spending, and the high Surplus of Budget Financing for the relevant year (SILPA), indicating inadequate fund utilization, ultimately contribute to the insignificant direct impact of RSF on economic growth.

RSF has a positive impact on the GRDP of regency/city in Papua Province because it serves as a significant source of revenue allocated from the central government to the regions, based on state revenues from taxes and natural resources in the region. This aligns with the fiscal theory of decentralization, which states that increasing the allocation of Revenue Sharing Funds (RSF) provides regional governments with the opportunity to increase capital and operational spending, which can stimulate regional economic growth. Tax RSF, which represents a portion of tax revenue distributed to regions, can be used to finance infrastructure, education, and health projects, which in turn contribute directly to increasing GRDP. As stated by Mardiasmo (2018), increased regional spending funded by RSF can stimulate local economic activity by increasing demand and creating jobs.

Revenue Sharing Funds from Natural Resources play a crucial role in boosting GRDP in resource-rich regions like Papua. Regions receiving RSF from Natural Resources, such as from the mining and forestry sectors, can utilize these funds to improve the quality of infrastructure and public services that support productive sectors. According to Utami et al. (2023), effective management of RSF from natural resources can increase the productivity of key economic sectors in the region, which in turn contributes to increasing GRDP. In the context of Papua, where many regions are rich in natural resources but still lag behind in infrastructure development, targeted allocation of Regional Revenue Sharing Funds (RSF) can reduce development gaps and encourage more inclusive economic growth.

The Special Autonomy Fund (SAF) variable has a coefficient of -1.073693 with a probability value of 0.3031. This indicates that the SAF has no effect on Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP). Therefore, an increase or decrease in the SAF does not significantly affect changes in GRDP. These results do not support the third hypothesis (H3), which states that the Special Autonomy Fund (SAF) has a significant effect on GRDP.

This study aligns with research by Widiprana (2022), which also stated that the Special Autonomy Fund had no significant effect on GRDP in the regency/city of West Papua Province from 2018 to 2021. This similar finding indicates that the allocation of the Special Autonomy Fund has not significantly impacted regional economic growth, as measured by GRDP, even though the funds are allocated to improve development and welfare in the region.

However, research conducted by Anwar et al. (2018) found that the Special Autonomy Fund had a significant positive effect on GRDP in the regency/city of Papua Province. In their study, using a fixed effects model, they found that the Special Autonomy Fund had a significant positive effect with a coefficient of 0.077388 and a probability value of 0.0002. These results indicate that the allocation of the Special Autonomy Fund is effective in increasing GRDP in the Papua region, which differs from the findings of this study. Furthermore, Fahrudin (2022) found that the Special Autonomy Fund (SAF) has an effect on economic growth.

The reason why the Special Autonomy Fund (SAF) has not had a significant impact on Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) in regency/city in Papua Province can be identified by the effective allocation and utilization of these funds. According to Malak (2012), a large budget will be meaningless if it is not managed properly. A substantial special autonomy fund will be of little benefit if its distribution and allocation are inaccurate. In some cases, massive development has occurred in the Papua region, funded by the special autonomy fund. Unfortunately, some of these development projects have only increased cash outflow rather than cash inflow. Inefficiencies in program implementation are often overlooked because they are masked by the large amount of the special autonomy fund.

Furthermore, research by Ardiansyah and Suyanto (2023) revealed several obstacles contributing to the ineffectiveness of the special allocation fund in increasing GRDP. These obstacles include inappropriate program targeting, budget constraints, extensive coverage of work areas, delays in fund transfers from the central government, and limited knowledge and capacity of human resources (HR). These obstacles result in the inability to implement planned programs optimally, and the goal of improving the welfare of the Papuan people has not been fully achieved. This was also stated by the Audit Board of Indonesia's Supreme Audit Agency (BPK) Opinion Team (2021), which, in its evaluation of the Special Autonomy Fund stated that a lack of human resource capacity, inadequate regulations, complex bureaucracy, geographical challenges, and a lack of transparency have led to the suboptimal use of funds. Regulatory improvements, increased human resource capacity, bureaucratic simplification, and increased commitment and transparency are needed to overcome these obstacles.

Overall, these findings align with the theory of fiscal federalism and fiscal decentralization, which examine how transfers from the central government to the regions affect regional economic performance, such as Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP). The results of simultaneous tests showing a significant effect of the General Allocation Fund (GAF), Revenue Sharing Fund (RSF), and Special Autonomy Fund (SAF) on GRDP support the main premise of these

theories. Fiscal federalism addresses the division of fiscal power between the central and regional governments. This theory argues that fiscal decentralization can improve the efficiency of public resource allocation because regional governments are more aware of their local needs than the central government.

Fiscal decentralization refers to the delegation of financial management authority from the central government to regional governments. This theory argues that decentralization can increase accountability, responsiveness, and efficiency in public financial management. According to Musgrave (1959), fiscal decentralization allows regional governments to tailor public services to local preferences and conditions, which can improve public welfare. Furthermore, various studies have shown that with decentralization, regional governments have stronger incentives to improve local economic performance because they are closer to and more accountable to their constituents. This leads to more appropriate and efficient public service delivery.

The results of the study, which show a significant influence of GAF, RSF, and SAF on GRDP, indicate that the allocation of funds from the central government to the regions can improve regional economic performance. The high coefficient of determination (0.977271) indicates that most of the variation in GRDP can be explained by these variables, which is consistent with the premise that fiscal decentralization can improve the economy. This result reflects that regional governments that receive larger funds have better capacity to provide public services and infrastructure, which in turn encourages regional economic growth. In other words, effective and efficient transfer of funds from the central government to the regions in accordance with the principles of fiscal federalism and fiscal decentralization can be a powerful tool to encourage local economic development and improve community welfare.

CONCLUSION

This study found that the General Allocation Fund (GAF) had a significant positive effect on Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) in regency/city in Papua Province. The increase in GAF significantly contributed to the increase in GRDP, indicating that the allocation of funds from the central government through GAF is effective in increasing regional economic activity. GAF can increase regional economic activity by increasing regional fiscal capacity. Revenue Sharing Funds (RSF) also had a significant positive effect on GRDP. An increase in RSF significantly contributed to the increase in GRDP. RSF is an important source of revenue that allows for increased capital and operational spending in the region. Thus, RSF serves as an effective mechanism to support regional economic growth, particularly in areas rich in natural resources. In contrast, the Special Autonomy Fund (SAF) did not significantly impact GRDP. Although the DAK is allocated to improve regional

development and welfare, the study results indicate that it has not yet succeeded in significantly impacting regional economic growth. This suggests that despite the significant potential in the allocation of GAF, the implementation and management of these funds may require improvement to achieve a more meaningful impact.

Thus, this study shows that the General Allocation Fund (GAF) and Revenue Sharing Fund (RSF) play a significant role in driving economic growth in Papua, while the Special Autonomy Fund (SAF) has not shown a significant impact. More effective and efficient fiscal policy implementation is needed to optimize the use of these funds to support equitable economic development in Papua Province.

Based on the research findings, there are at least three recommendations for the government. First, increasing the effectiveness of fund use. The government needs to ensure that funds allocated through the GAF, RSF, and SAF are used effectively and efficiently for projects that can improve economic growth and public welfare in Papua. Second, monitoring and evaluation. Improving oversight and evaluation of fund use by local governments to ensure that funds are used according to their intended purpose and produce the desired impact. Third, increasing regional capacity. Providing training and technical assistance to local governments to enhance their capacity to manage funds and implement effective development programs.

However, there are several limitations that need to be considered for further research. First, this study did not delve deeper into how the GAF, RSF, and SAF are used in each district/city. However, the effectiveness of fund use can vary across regions. These limitations highlight the importance of further analysis of the allocation and use of funds at the regional level. Second, this study did not account for non-fiscal factors that can influence economic growth, such as the quality of human resources, infrastructure, and other non-fiscal policies. Third, it did not consider economic disparities and poverty levels in the Papua region. Economic inequality and poverty can provide a different context for GRDP. Acknowledging these limitations, it is hoped that further research can be conducted to deepen our understanding of the impact of fiscal decentralization funds on economic growth in Papua Province and other regions in Indonesia.

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